

Dependence of Selectivity Coefficient on Ionic Hydration and Debye-Hückel Parameter a° in the Desorption of $[\text{Co en}_3]^{+3}$ ion from H-Coen₃-bentonite

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As the knowledge of adsorption and desorption of trivalent complex cations viz. trisethylenediamine cobaltic¹ and hexammine cobaltic ions² on and from a bentonite clay is still meagre, attempts have been made to study the fundamental details of the processes. In this communication, the selectivities of the desorbing ions from H-Coen₃-bentonite have been interpreted on the basis of ionic hydration³ and the Debye-Hückel parameter a° ⁴ using a number of mono and divalent cations (NH_4^+ , K^+ , Rb^+ , Cs^+ , Na^+ , Li^+ , Ca^{+2} , Ba^{+2} and Mg^{+2}).

A bentonite fraction having particle size $< 2.0\mu$ was isolated and collected by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation of Rajasthan bentonite (supplied by Calcutta Minerals Supply Co. Ltd.)

It was converted into the hydrogen form by resin (Amberlite I.R.-120 & Dowex 2X-4) treatment and its base exchange capacity (b.e.c) was determined by titration with baryta in presence of 1M BaCl_2 solution using phenolphthalein as indicator. The value was found to be 100.0 m.e./100 gm. For studying desorption, 10 ml. portions of the hydrogen bentonite suspension (varying from 1.55 to 1.85%) were treated with Coen_3Cl_3 in concentrations approximately two times the b.e.c. of the clay in a number of test tubes, to which varying amounts of different electrolytes were added. The upper limit of the final concentration of the electrolytes was kept about 0.3 M. The mixtures were shaken for 2 hr. and allowed to equilibrate overnight, centrifuged for 15 minutes or so and the Coen_3Cl_3 content was estimated by means of absorbance measurement. Preliminary experiments showed that the same state of equilibrium was obtained if Coen_3^{+3} was adsorbed first and then desorbed with electrolytes, and hence the procedure described above was followed.

The results of the investigations are summarized in Fig 1. (a & b). It is clear from the graph that Rb^+ and Cs^+ are more strongly attached than their hydrated ionic radii require. It is also apparent that they cause a sharp break in the log (selectivity coefficient) vs. hydrated ionic radius curve, the positions of NH_4^+ and K^+ are, however, intermediate between the positions occupied by the two pairs of Rb^+ , Cs^+ and Na^+ , Li^+ . On the other hand if the parameter a° is considered to be the index of ionic size and $\log K$, where K is the selectivity coefficient, is plotted against $1/a^\circ$, a straight line is obtained. The results strongly suggest that in such a process of desorption of trivalent complex cation

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from the clay surface, the parameter a° rather than the hydrated ionic radius may be utilized to correlate the affinities of the univalent and bivalent cations for the expanding type clay minerals viz., montmorillonite. Similar results have been reported by us in connection

FIG. 1a & 1b

Correlation of Selectivity Coefficient with hydrated ionic radius (Fig 1a) and Debye Hückel parameter a° (Fig. 1b).

with the studies of hexammine cobaltic chloride on bentonite and by Kressman and Kitchener⁵ in their studies on phenol-sulphonate resin exchangers. The plot of log K vs. $1/a^\circ$ is however on the basis of the simple model of Pauley⁶, the essential feature of which is the electrostatic attraction between the counter ions and the fixed ionic groups. It is assumed that all the counter ions in the ion exchanger are found at their distance of closest approach to the fixed ionic groups. This model leads qualitatively to the preference of the ion exchanger for the counter ions with the smaller a° values and counter ions of higher valencies. Attempts have also been undertaken to explain similar results on the basis of other theoretical approaches and models. Further work is in progress.

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